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Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional **MED**iterranean **G**rape, **OL**ive and **D**urum wheat food systems

Deliverable 4.7

Second Feedback report from users on durum wheat pilot service development

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The following points summarize the main contents reported in this deliverable on the second feedback on the climate service pilot(s), which is collected internally among the WP4 partners. In fact, this internal feedback temporarily substitutes the user feedback that was supposed to be collected as a result of the workshop cancelled because of covid19.

- The feedback on CLISAGRI (previously called Ragroclim) is provided in detail by HORTA agronomists. The implementation of DELPHI on seasonal climate forecasts as well as the MED-GOLD products integration in the framework of the MED-GOLD Dashboard are evaluated and discussed by BARILLA. The last progres of GRANODURO.NET is documented. However, the feedback by the GRANODURO.NET end users, which necessarily requires a dedicated workshop, is postponed to the future.
- This internal feedback includes a discussion of the limitation and the difficulty that are encountered in handling seasonal forecast data, interpreting the results, as well as future expectations for the MED-GOLD tools. Therefore, the procedure for preparing the seasonal forecast data for the MED-GOLD tools is described in detail.
- Future steps will include further development of these tools accounting for the outcomes of this deliverable in preparation of D4.2 on the “Design of innovative agro-climatic systems for durum wheat” and to the presentation to the end users in order to collect their feedback as well.
- Additional efforts will be devoted in paving the way to improve the quality of the seasonal climate forecast data handling and in applying the developed techniques to decadal climate predictions and future climate scenarios. The extent of the last activity will be upscaled at the global level, in order to assess the changes of suitability of areas currently growing durum wheat and to establish the emergence of new suitable areas because of climate change, as requested by BARILLA.

With this deliverable, the project has contributed to the achievement of the following objectives (DOA, PartB Table1.1):

No.	Objective	Yes
1	To co-design, co-develop, test, and assess the added value of proof-of-concept climate services for olive, grape, and durum wheat	X
2	To refine, validate, and upscale the three pilot services with the wider European and global user communities for olive, grape, and durum wheat	
3	To ensure replicability of MED-GOLD climate services in other crops/climates (e.g., coffee) and to establish links to policy making globally	
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	X

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. PURPOSE

Reducing the risks associated with weather and climate extremes is of key importance to ensure a sustainable durum wheat production. To deal with these challenges, farmers require a reliable decision support system based on seasonal climate predictions, providing timely information on key drivers causing reduction in yield quantity and quality. This information can help farmers in making crucial decisions, such as planning of sowing dates, selection of variety, seed treatments, fertilization management, pest and disease management and other field operations (RD.1). Indeed, the previous user feedback report (RD.2) confirmed a first broad success of the level of development of these tools by end-users, which have seen their general expectations being met.

The purpose of this deliverable is to describe the current level of implementation and results of the MED-GOLD tools for the durum wheat climate pilot service developed by WP4. In particular, this deliverable focuses on the implementation of CLISAGRI (previously called Ragroclim), DELPHI and GRANODURO.NET on seasonal forecast data and paves the ways for the applications at the decadal time scale as well as at the long-term scale characterizing global warming.

This report collects the internal feedback among WP4 partners on the seasonal forecast data and on the current results of the MED-GOLD tools applied to such data. In particular, HORTA is providing feedback on CLISAGRI indicators. BARILLA is providing feedback on DELPHI implemented on seasonal forecast data and on the general development of the MED-GOLD tools at larger spatial scales and longer temporal scales as well as in the MED-GOLD Dashboard, which is a new climate information visualization platform whose conceptualization has been imported by WP3.

The feedback on the GRANODURO.NET platforms with the integration of seasonal forecast data driving a phenological model coupled to risk indicators for the main diseases affecting durum wheat is planned for a next deliverable, after a dedicated workshop can take place.

1.2. SCOPE

This deliverable contributes defining the final shape of the climate service prototype that will bear the capability of being used operationally, also by different actors than the project partners. For this purpose, this report propotes as much as possible the replicability aspect of all the tools that have been developed by providing detailed descriptions and specific references. The outcomes of this report will define the content of the upcoming deliverable D4.2 ("Design of innovative agro-climatic systems for durum wheat") as well as the activity plan till the end of the project.

1.3. DEFINITIONS AND ACRONYMS

1.3.1. Definitions

Concepts and terms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Table 1-1 Definitions

Concept / Term	Definition
GRANODURO.NET	This is the DSS developed by HORTA for the durum wheat providers of BARILLA
DELPHI	This is the JRC model providing durum wheat yield outlooks to BARILLA
ICT Platform	This is the platform download, processing and redistributing seasonal forecast data in MED-GOLD

1.3.2. ACRONYMS

Acronyms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Table 1-2 Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
CLISAGRI	CLimate SERvice for Agriculture (formerly called RagroCLIM, RD.1)
CDS	Climate Data Store
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
DSS	Decision Support System
CSTools	Climate Service Tools (see RD.6)
ICT	Information and Communication Technology

2. REFERENCES

2.1 REFERENCE DOCUMENTS

The following documents, although not part of this document, amplify or clarify its contents. Reference documents are those not applicable and referenced within this document. They are referenced in this document in the form [RD.x]:

Table 2-1 Reference Documents

Ref.	Title	Code	Version	Date
[RD.1]	MED-GOLD deliverable 4.1 - Report on the identified specific needs and opportunities			2018
[RD.2]	MED-GOLD deliverable 4.6 - First Feedback report from users on durum wheat pilot service development			2019
[RD.3]	Frías, M. D., Iturbide, M., Manzanas, R., Bedia, J., Fernández, J., Herrera, S., ... & Gutiérrez, J. M. (2018). An R package to visualize and communicate uncertainty in seasonal climate prediction. <i>Environmental modelling & software</i> , 99, 101-110.			2018
[RD.4]	Ceglar et al. RAgroClim: An R package for agro-climate services (submitted)			2020
[RD.5]	MED-GOLD deliverable 3.7 - Second Feedback report from users on wine pilot service development			2020
[RD.6]	Nuria Perez-Zanon, Louis-Philippe Caron, Carmen Alvarez-Castro, Jost von Hardenberg, Llorenç LLEDó, Nicolau Manubens, Eroteida Sanchez-Garcia, Bert van Schaeybroeck, Veronica Torralba and Deborah Verfaillie (2020). CStools: Assessing Skill of Climate Forecasts on Seasonal-to-Decadal Timescales. R package version 3.0.0. https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=CStools			2020
[RD.7]	Biavetti, I., Karetzos, S., Ceglar, A., Toreti, A., Panagos, P., (2014). European meteorological data: contribution to research, development, and policy support. In: Proc. SPIE 9229, Second International Conference on Remote Sensing and Geoinformation of the Environment, Cyprus, https://doi.org/10.1117.12.2066286			2014

3. ACTIONS LINKED TO THE 1ST PARTICIPATORY WORKSHOP

3.1. SUMMARY OF THE MAIN OUTCOME FROM THE PREVIOUS PARTICIPATORY WORKSHOPS

After the first assessment of user needs documented in [RD.1], the implementation of the climate service prototype for the durum wheat sector has gone through a first round of review, which is documented in [RD.2]. The service developed for the durum wheat sector builds on the use of 3 key technologies:

- The platform GRANODURO.NET which provides support to farmers' decisions based on the outcome of a phenological model.
- A set of R scripts developed by JRC (CLISAGRI, formerly called Ragroclim) in order to compute bioclimatic indicators during the various phenological phases of durum wheat varieties.
- The yield model DELPHI, maintained by CNR, providing seasonal yield outlooks for Barilla.

The key outcomes of the previous interactions with growers and elevators can be summarized as follows

1. The use of seasonal forecast as input for GRANODURO.NET requires the bias correction of daily data of temperature and rainfall in order to produce usable information for durum wheat producers.
2. A strategy for the visualization of bio-climatic indicators has been validated with the users, consistent with the information which is already included in GRANODURO.NET.
3. A list of 16 bioclimatic indicators (see ANNEX A) have been identified to be implemented in CLISAGRI as an additional source of information for GRANODURO.NET, with priority to hydrological balance, excessive wetness, cold stress and heat stress related indicators.
4. Accessing historical record of the CLISAGRI bioclimatic indicators is a useful information for growers for giving context to the current situation in the field.

Additional feedback has been collected from BARILLA regarding the use of seasonal forecast as an input for the model DELPHI, namely:

- A. The interpretation of the seasonal outlooks based on probabilistic ensemble members of climate predictions is straightforward as it is perceived as the extension of a consolidated practice.
- B. The raw data of the ensemble members of seasonal predictions do not bring significant improvements on the established practice of producing seasonal outlooks based on climatology and on the evaluation of dry/wet scenarios.
- C. The MED-GOLD tools require the bias correction of the raw seasonal forecast data as well as a thorough assessment of the reliability of the seasonal predictions.

3.2 UPGRADES IMPLEMENTED IN THE TOOL FOLLOWING THE FEEDBACK OF THE PREVIOUS WORKSHOPS.

Based on the indications summarized in section 3.1 a number of upgrades have been implemented in order to create a service that better matches the expectations of the users. A full description of the developments implemented to enhance the services will be described in D4.2 which will describe the *Design of innovative agro-climatic systems for durum wheat*. However a quick point by point summary of the key activities is reported to support the discussion on the further feedback collected or expected from the users.

1. The seasonal forecasts data preparation is discussed in section 3.2.1. It includes the bias correction of daily data has been implemented by ENEA using the algorithms available within the R package CStools (RD.6). Two data streams have been created: a) csv files containing data on single grid points are made available as an input for GRANODURO.NET and b) NetCDF files containing gridded data on selected areas are made available for the platform DELPHI and for the computation of bioclimatic indicators on larger areas. An additional strategy for the visualization of seasonal forecast data has been implemented by ENEA based on consolidated practices such as the “dashboard” described in RD.3.
2. Section 3.2.2 reports the upgrades of GRANODURO.NET and the operational coupling with bias-corrected seasonal forecast data. GRANODURO.NET already included the CLISAGRI bioclimatic indicators in the historical analysis. For the seasonal forecasts HORTA implemented new risk diseases indicators as well. These are computed for the sensitive period predicted by the phenological model of durum wheat varieties, calibrated with observed field data.
3. Section 3.2.3 described the current development of CLISAGRI (formerly called Ragroclim) as well as an example of implementation with seasonal forecast data.
4. Section 3.2.4 reports a synthesis of the extensive validation of yield forecasts based on the DELPHY system coupled with seasonal forecast data before and after bias correction.

3.2.1 SEASONAL FORECASTS DATA PREPARATION.

Integration of seasonal climate forecasts into decision support systems is becoming a highly important component of climate service development. This has recently become possible due to better understanding of relevant processes in the climate system, especially when it comes to spatio-temporal features of climate extremes and their precursor mechanisms.

Seasonal forecast data of monthly and daily mean data for mean temperature, maximum temperature, minimum temperature and precipitation is obtained from the ECMWF System-5 (SEAS5, www.ecmwf.int/en/newsletter/154/meteorology/ecmwfs-new-long-range-forecasting-system-seas5). The long-range forecasts consists of 51 ensemble members, initialized at the beginning of every month, and integrated for 7 months. For the purpose of this project we use a set of retrospective seasonal forecasts (re-forecasts) from 1993 until 2019, that can be compared to observed historical climate data. This set of re-forecasts consists of 25 ensemble members. The

objective is to provide users with the probabilities of the durum wheat plant to reach its critical phase (flowering) with months in advance for the three Italian locations, which are Ravenna, Foggia and Jesi (RD.1). For that aim, raw and bias-adjusted seasonal predictions of the historical period are used as input in the phenological models and in all involved computations. The involved data include daily seasonal predictions of precipitation, maximum and minimum temperature from ECMWF SEAS5 prediction system obtained from C3S considering the start dates from November and from the subsequent months along the growing season of the different durum wheat varieties (ending in July at last).

To reduce the biases associated with the predictions, we have applied a simple bias adjustment approach (quantile mapping) in cross-validation to correct the raw predictions obtained from SEAS5 considering the JRC-Agri4Cast data as reference dataset (RD.7). The results of the bias correction are discussed in the section describing DELPHI results and implemented already in the other MED-GOLD tools.

ERA5 reanalysis is also used as a reference climatological data in addition to the JRC dataset. ERA5 reanalysis combines past observations with models to generate consistent time series of multiple climate variables (Cy41r2, 2016). The surface fields of minimum and maximum daily temperature and daily precipitation cumulates were obtained from the C3S resolution of 0.25 degrees. Temperature fields were regridded to 1 degree grid (same as seasonal re-forecasts) using bilinear mapping, while conservative remapping was used to upscale daily precipitation.

3.2.2 UPGRADES IMPLEMENTED IN GRANODURO.NET.

HORTA implementation of CLISAGRI bioclimatic indicators for the observed past climate variability has been discussed in D4.6 (RD.2) and integrated here. The analysis of the past is actually one of the tools requested by users in order to better interpret the results of the seasonal forecasts.

Figure 3-1: Example time-series for one of the CLISAGRI bioclimatic indicators, the observed number of heat days ($T_{max} > 38^{\circ}\text{C}$) around flowering in one of the target locations for the years from 1976 to 2018.

Figure 3-1 shows an example result of the implementation of CLISAGRI on GRANODURO.NET for one of the bioclimatic indicators for durum wheat identified by the users (D4.6 – RD.2).

HORTA also implemented the seasonal forecast data in the GRANODURO.NET platform for predicting the phenological stages and the risk of diseases. For the three MED-GOLD case studies (Ravenna, Jesi, Foggia) the phenological model and indexes for the main wheat diseases are calculated using seasonal forecasts. For each location, the phenological model is run considering three wheat varieties, which have a development cycle of different length (short, average and long). The phenological model runs on the base of weather data starting from the sowing date, and simulates the crop development on the base of weather data, and takes into consideration wheat variety specific characteristics. Main phases identified by the model are wheat emergence, tillering, stem elongation, booting, heading, flowering and maturity.

Indexes for the forecast of the risk posed by the main diseases affecting durum wheat have been elaborated. Diseases taken into consideration are: stripe rust (caused by *Puccinia striiformis*), leaf rust (caused by *Puccinia triticina*), stem rust (caused by *Puccinia graminis* subs. *graminis*), powdery mildew (caused by *Erisiphe graminis* f.sp.*tritici*), Septoria blotch (caused by *Mycosphaerella graminicola* and *Leptosphaeria nodorum*) and Fusarium Head blight (caused by fungi of the genus *Fusarium*, mainly *F. graminearum* and *F. culmorum*). The indexes are calculated on the base of the

sole weather data, taking into consideration conditions favouring the fungal development. Indexes are calculated for periods in which they can pose a problem to the crop, defined on the base of wheat phenology. The employed phenological model is validated using the HORTA dataset for each starting date of the bias corrected seasonal forecasts. Figure 3-2 represents an example of such validation.

Figure 3-2: Seasonal forecast timing of phenological phases for a medium variety (Homer) in Jesi. The panels show the difference between the observed dates and the simulation ensembles starting at different times during the growing season.

Figure 3-2 shows an example of validation of HORTA phenological model driver by seasonal forecast data, after bias correction. The spread tends to reduce as long as the starting date on the simulations progresses. The general bias tends to reduce as well, albeit not monotonically.

Figure 3-3: Example of seasonal forecast integration in GRANODURO.NET: phenology and risk of diseases. The y-axis indicates the phenological stage (in italian). The x-axis report the time during the growing season ending in July, in this case. The shaded area represents the spread of the simulation ensemble. The coloured bars on the bottom represent the risk of disease: a) risk of days favouring the infection in the sensitive period; b) number of cycles of the disease with respect of all the possible cycles in the period.

MED-GOLD - Granoduro.net, Indici di rischio malattie

Località: JESI | Varietà: Homer | RUN: 2017.01
Ruggine bruna

(a) Rischio di giorni favorevoli all'infezione per periodo di suscettibilità alla malattia
(b) Rischio relativo al n° di cicli di malattia previsti sul totale di cicli possibili nel periodo

Figure 3-3 shows an example of integration between the predicted phenological stages and a disease risk indicator for Jesi, considering an average variety ‘Homer’ and a particular disease (leaf rust). This information potentially allows planning the protection threstments well ahead in time. All other varieties are considered as well, and also different diseases such as stripe rust, stem rust, powdery mildew, Septoria blotch and Fusarium Head Blight. The analysis is conducted for the other MED-GOLD target locations (Foggia and Ravenna).

3.2.3 UPGRADES IMPLEMENTED IN CLISAGRI (EX RAGROCLIM).

CLISAGRI is the R package for agro-climate services, developed by the JRC, which was referred as “RagroClim” in report D4.7. However, the development of this software developed steadily and the number of applications within the project increased as well.

In fact, CLISAGRI integrates a dynamic crop phenology model with an approach based on dedicated bioclimatic indicators to assess the severity of climate extremes during sensitive crop growth stages. Given the generality of the approach, CLISAGRI application is envisaged also for olives and grapes (RD.5).

Regarding durum wheat, the initial set of the agro-climate indicators has been developed in a co-design approach with a consortium of durum wheat farmers during the first MED-GOLD stage of users feedback (RD.2). The four groups of indicators characterize hydrological balance, excessive wetness, cold stress and heat stress are listed in ANNEX A, together with the agronomic evaluation that is provided by HORTA.

It is worth noting that most water related indicators are based on standardized precipitation anomalies, which are difficult to forecast accurately. The internal feedback obtained regarding the predictability of precipitation triggered a new development on the extraction and communication of probabilistic information from the ensemble of seasonal forecast simulations. A new option allows separating the analysis of the past climate variability from the computation of the indexes in the current season. This option is currently under testing.

The dynamic phenology model and agro-climatic indicators have been implemented as a new R package called CLISAGRI. This includes two options at different levels of complexity, one with two growing degree day sum indicators and one with six growing degree day sum indicators, suitable to describe the climatic effects on the timing of the development stages of durum wheat. The software includes a calibration procedure that employs observational data of phenological phase succession for different durum wheat varieties (e.g. HORTA dataset).

Figure 3-4: Schematic representation of the four groups of indicators that are identified by the end-users in order to characterize hydrological balance, excessive wetness, cold stress and heat stress conditions through the phenological phases of durum wheat.

The package also provides a set of optimization functions, which target optimal variety selection in terms of crop cycle duration to avoid unfavourable weather events during the sensitive growth stages that will become useful for breeders, once CLISAGRI will be applied to decadal predictions and climate change scenarios.

Figure 3-5: Simulated hydrological balance between heading and maturity (panel a) and number of hot days between flowering and maturity, based on durum wheat varieties characterized by different combinations of TSUM1/TSUM2 (indicated by different colors). To distinguish between different combinations, the color of each simulated indicator is related to scale in panel c, with each color representing a unique combination of TSUM1/TSUM2. The R code to produce the indicator of type 16 (number of hot days) is shown in panel b.

Figure 3-5 shows a breeding exercise conducted for the past by considering two important MED-GOLD indicators as proxy of drought and heat stress. Different combinations of the phenological parameters related to Tsum1 and Tsum2 define potential varieties that can be obtained by breeding. This powerful tool provides a simple way to derive clear results as, in this case, the combination of genes to limit heat stress between flowering and maturity, which is detrimental for the final yield. The figure also shows an example of how to use the software, to allow the replicability of this result.

At this stage of the project, CLISAGRI has been successfully implemented in seasonal forecasts (see Figure 3-6).

Figure 3-6: Seasonal forecast of CLISAGRI indicator hydrological balance between sowing and maturity (November to June) for Italy in growing season 2018/2019. The April run has been used here to provide the seasonal forecast data; to complete the time series of climatic data for entire season, the data from the first half of growing season (already observed until the issue of April seasonal forecast) were obtained from ERA5 meteorological fields. The size of the circle indicates the ranked probability skill score of seasonal forecasts - higher values indicate better skill and higher added values of seasonal forecasts with respect to climatological values.

Figure 3-6 represents an example of seasonal forecast of hydrological balance between sowing and maturity of durum wheat in Italy for the growing season 2018/19. This example integrates observed data from sowing in autumn until April with seasonal forecast from the beginning of April until the end of growing season (in Italy generally occurring in June). The seasonal forecast for 2019 indicates an equal (likely) probability of being both in the normal and in the above normal categories because a similar number of members are predicting normal and above normal categories and it is not possible to choose between the two of them.

3.2.4 UPGRADES IMPLEMENTED IN DELPHI.

The DELPHI system has been implemented using driving climate data provided by Copernicus Data Store released in October 2017 and consisting of 51 forecast simulations lasting for 6 months (see Section 3.1.1). Results are compared with the results of the standard implementation Delphi System that is driven by synthetic weather scenarios based on historical observations (dry, average, wet scenario).

For each simulation the input weather files were built as indicated in Figure 3-7.

Figure 3-7: configuration of the forcing data for the DELPHI simulation during the different phases of the growing season. Observation and simulated data used for the forcing are merged in different proportions ensuring the closest consistency with reality and growing accuracy as long as the end of the growing season is approached. Scenario data indicates the seasonal forecast members. AVG Scenario refers to the average conditions based on long-term weather observations i.e. the climatology.

For the three MED-GOLD case studies (Jesi, Ravenna, Foggia) yield and biomass predictions are calculated at a monthly time step, starting from October 1st. The results with all the ensembles members and the Dry-Average-Wet scenarios results and charts with average, percentiles 25-75 for all ensembles predictions, are provided to BARILLA and will constitute the basis for the DELPHI internal feedback reported later. This section summarizes the result for yield.

Figure 3-8: Delphi system implemented using driving climate data from CDS seasonal forecasts (left panels) and standard DELPHI implementation driven by synthetic weather scenarios based on historical observations (dry, average, wet scenario) for the three MED-GOLD target locations: Jesi (top panels), Ravenna (middle panels) and Foggia (bottom panels) during season 2018/2019.

Figure 3-8 shows the comparison between the results of the new DELPHI system implemented for MED-GOLD, driven by seasonal forecast data, and the traditional DELPHI system, driven by a mix of current observations and analogue scenarios observed in the past. In Jesi, the seasonal forecast

scenario range is narrower than that provided by the Dry-Average-Wet scenario. The results show a better performance for the predictions provided with seasonal forecast.

In Jesi (top panels) Seasonal forecast scenario range is narrower than that provided by the Dry-Average-Wet scenario until March 1st, with a tendency to underestimate yield value. In Ravenna (middle panels), Seasonal forecast scenario range is wider than that provided by the Dry-Average-Wet scenario, with a tendency, for both scenario systems, to underestimate yield value. It is worth noting that these simulations are conducted with forcing fields that are not bias corrected yet. In Foggia, seasonal forecast scenario range is narrower than that provided by the Dry-Average-Wet scenario until March 1st.

Analysis of the results at daily time scale is provided to BARILLA as well. The analysis following the MED-GOLD ‘bad years’ and ‘good years’ narrative has been conducted into a deep level of detail and partially reported here. Simulations for the ‘bad’ and ‘good’ years are conducted as well. The bad years (below average yield) that are considered for further investigation are 2010 for Ravenna and 2007 for Foggia and Ancona. Good year (above average yield) are 2012 for Ravenna and 2016 for Foggia and Ancona. These particular simulations are based on the climate data provided by ICT platform released in February and in April for each crop year (25 ensemble members for 6 months of forecast). As in the previous case, results were compared with the results of the traditional Delphi System by feeding the model with synthetic weather scenarios based on historical observations (dry, average, wet scenario). For each simulation the input weather files are built as indicated in Figure 3-9.

Figure 3-9: as figure 3-7, but for the ‘bad year’ and ‘good years’ MED-GOLD narrative (see text for explanations).

Figure 3-10: Results for yield prediction on the first day of June for each crop season on the basis of three historical scenarios (red-green-blue circle) and on the basis of seasonal forecast (black square) for Ravenna in 2010 (bad year). For each year the predicted yield by feeding the model with only observed weather data is also reported (grey circle). The left panel is based on the raw CDS output. The left panel is based on the bias corrected data provided by the MED-GOLD ICT platform.

Figure 3-10 shows a particular example of ‘bad years – good years’ analysis. It is interesting to note how the final yield is included in the seasonal forecast spread, which is reduced at later stages in the growing season. The bias correction significantly improves the accuracy of the ensemble mean prediction starting in April. Results for other locations and years are provided to BARILLA in order to allow the internal feedback. These results are summarized in Table 1.

Table 3-1: Summary of yield statistics obtained with DELPHI computed from seasonal forecast starting in November and February with and without bias correction.

FEBRUARY		BIASED			UNBIASED			YIELD_REF (t/ha)
GOOD_YEAR	MIN	MAX	MEAN	MIN	MAX	MEAN		
RAVENNA	4.44	7.32	5.56	3.30	6.81	5.23	6.55	
ANCONA	1.67	3.16	2.35	1.48	2.66	2.13	5.50	
FOGGIA	2.46	4.83	3.71	2.86	4.82	4.03	5.17	
BAD_YEAR								
RAVENNA	2.98	5.59	4.14	2.91	4.93	3.99	4.64	
ANCONA	1.78	2.85	2.29	1.94	3.16	2.43	3.72	
FOGGIA	2.28	4.98	3.45	2.86	4.64	3.52	2.77	

APRIL		BIASED			UNBIASED			YIELD_REF (t/ha)
GOOD_YEAR	MIN	MAX	MEAN	MIN	MAX	MEAN		
RAVENNA	6.08	9.07	7.35	4.19	8.92	6.85	6.55	
ANCONA	4.40	8.17	6.38	4.55	6.98	5.74	5.50	
FOGGIA	5.59	6.95	6.29	5.28	7.03	6.08	5.17	
BAD_YEAR								
RAVENNA	4.56	5.59	5.12	4.13	5.53	4.78	4.64	
ANCONA	1.87	2.87	2.43	1.44	3.13	2.41	3.72	
FOGGIA	2.43	3.56	3.12	2.66	3.52	3.16	2.77	

The CNR also performed an analysis of the seasonal forecast driven DELPHI system comparing the raw COPERNICUS data to the bias corrected data generated by MED-GOLD. This analysis is conducted for period 1988 – 2018 considering 25 ensemble members starting in February. The schematics of the forcing configuration for this experiments is provided in Figure 3-11.

Figure 3-11: as figure 3-7, but for the ‘bias’ vs. ‘unbiased’ seasonal forecast simulations.

Results were compared with the results of the current Delphi System by feeding the model with ERA5 reanalysis dataset synthetic weather scenarios based on historical observations (dry, average, wet scenario).

Figure 3-12. Results for yield prediction at harvesting time for each crop season on the basis of seasonal forecast (ensemble members black circles and green line ensemble mean) are reported. For each year the predicted yield by feeding the model with only ERA5 reanalysis data is also reported (red line). Both analysis are reported by using biased seasonal forecast (left panel) and unbiased seasonal forecast (right panel).

For each analysis the average bias (difference between simulations with seasonal forecast and simulations with ERA5) and the Pearson correlation coefficient were calculated both using the biased and unbiased dataset. The same analysis carried out using the synthetic weather scenarios based on historical observations (dry, average, wet scenario) are reported to BARILLA in order to allow them providing their feedbacks.

For Foggia case study a significant improvement is reported in the use of unbiased data. The final performances (bias and correlation) are higher than those obtained by using historical observations (dry, average, wet scenario).

For Ancona case study (not shown, but shared with BARILLA) no improvement is reported in the use of unbiased data. The final performances (bias and correlation coefficient, r) are similar to those obtained by using historical observations (wet scenario).

For Ravenna case study (not shown, but shared with BARILLA) no improvement is reported in the use of unbiased data as well. The final performances (bias and r) are lower than those obtained by

using historical observations (dry, average and wet scenario). These results are summarised in Figure 3-13.

Figure 3-13. Relative skill in terms of predicting yield above/below the average, provided with a qualitative indicator of making a hit (right forecast of a crop year with yield higher/lower than average) or making a false alarm. Below the total hits expressed as % for yield simulations based on biased seasonal forecast (bias), unbiased seasonale forecast (unbias) and climatology (dry-average-wet) for Foggia-Ancona-Ravenna case studies.

% (bias/unbias)

0.0 70.9 48.4 48.4 38.7 38.7

% (dry/average/wet)

0.0 - 0.0 - 45 0.0 - 0.0 - 58 61 - 67 - 42

Figure 3-13 confirms that the unbiased dataset performs better in Foggia Case Study. No improvement is found in Ancona nor Ravenna. Ancona forecast based on wet scenario has higher

skill than forecast based both on biased and unbiased dataset. Ravenna forecast based on dry/average/wet scenario bears higher skill than forecast based both on biased and unbiased dataset. The same analysis but for the skill in predicting the interannual variability has been provided to BARILLA.

4. CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE CO-DESIGN OF THE SECTORAL TOOLS

4.1. FEEDBACK FROM BARILLA ON THE THE MED-GOLD DASHBOARD

The development of the [MED-GOLD Dashboard](#) has started as a direct response to the user needs emerged in WP3 for the wine sector, where the implementation of a platform for the visualization of climate information was recognized as a key component of the prototype service already during the early stages of the project. The specific need for a data visualization tool did not emerge in WP4, as GRANODURO.NET has already an established role in the landscape of decision support tools for the durum wheat sector.

A detailed account of the co-design and co-development process of the MED-GOLD Dashboard is reported in DEL3.7 [RD.5]. In particular, the development of the MED-GOLD Dashboard has been based on the FUNCTIONAL SPECIFICATIONS document reported [here](#) (version Nov 25th, 2019). Please note that some parts (including some variables and features) colored in red in the text, are not included in the first version of MED-GOLD Dashboard but will be present in the future releases. Moreover, several open points are still present in the working document and will be addressed before the final release of the demonstrator.

The team working on the development of the MED-GOLD dashboard, composed by ENEA, BeeToBIT and UTH has decided to take the opportunity of the co-development process started in WP3 to engage additional potential users at BARILLA and set the ground to enhance the replicability and foster the scale-up of the prototype service in other sub-sectors and in other geographical areas. In order to assure an effective co-development of the MED-GOLD Dashboard, during the development phase of the first release (initially planned for the first months of 2020), a number of periodic “sprint meetings” with ICT partners Beetobit and UTH, in charge of technical development of the application, ENEA and the MED-GOLD industrial partners (Barilla, DCOOP and SOGRAPE) have been organized every two weeks, starting from January 29th 2020. All other MED-GOLD partners possibly interested could also attend these meetings.

Chiara Monotti, the focal point for MED-GOLD at BARILLA, has participated to all of the “sprint meetings” (see DEL3.7, RD.5) that have been organized on a bi-weekly basis between January 2020 and May 2020 in order to let the users follow closely the development of the MED_GOLD Dashboard and provide early feedbacks on on the work in progress.

The engagement with BARILLA in the co-development has proven extremely effective in creating awareness on the potential usefulness of the dashboard and on rising interest in the possibility to

replicate the functionalities of the dashboard for indicators relevant for the durum wheat sector and in other cultivation areas.

The feedback from BARILLA has been collected both during the sprint meetings and during dedicated phone calls and email exchanges and are reported in Table 1 below. It is worth noting that all feedback has been collected during remote meetings as the co-development of the Dashboard coincided mostly with the lockdown period due to the COVID-19 emergency. However, teleconferences and phone calls have proven useful in establishing a fruitful dialogue which has created values on both sides. On one hand, the co-development process has been enriched with new input, while Barilla had the opportunity to be exposed to detailed technical discussions which have played the role of field training on new concepts and methodologies.

The only physical meeting between BARILLA and ENEA took place on January 9th at ENEA headquarters in Rome. The meeting was focused on discussing the characteristics, advantages and limitations of climate information at different time scales, from a few days to decades and centuries. This meeting highlighted the importance of training the users of climate information on concepts that might not be immediately evident even to highly educated professionals with limited knowledge on climate science (e.g. time scales, reliability, skill, statistical ensembles etc). The content of this informal meeting is reflected largely in the webinar that has been prepared by the MED-GOLD partners on the *Time scales of Climate Services for the agriculture sector*, which is available on the MED-GOLD [web site](https://www.med-gold.eu/2020/04/24/webinar-time-scales-of-climate-services-for-agriculture/) (<https://www.med-gold.eu/2020/04/24/webinar-time-scales-of-climate-services-for-agriculture/>). In this respect, projects like MED-GOLD prove to be effective *Discussion Support Platforms* where professional with specialized competences in specific areas can effectively interact and create new shared knowledge.

Table 4-1. Feedbacks from BARILLA on the co-development of the MED-GOLD dashboard.

Source	Feedback
Sprint Meeting	The MED-GOLD Dashboard is very informative and well designed. The chart with hindcast data in the seasonal forecast panel needs more explanation
Sprint Meeting	It would be useful to export the data for further analysis
Teleconference with ENEA	The MED-GOLD Dashboard seems a useful resource for durum wheat. BARILLA would be interested in using the bio-climatic indicators implemented in the package CLISAGRI visualized with the same strategy, for the historical, seasonal and long-term projections. In the long term projections it would be useful to include future yield estimates from the model Wofost.
Teleconference with ENEA	The main areas of interest around the Mediterranean are Italy, Spain, France and Turkey. The optimal solution is to use seasonal forecast at

	<p>the highest possible spatial resolution. If this is not achievable for technical reasons it is also useful to access outlook over large geographical areas (e.g. entire Europe) and then focus on more specific areas at a higher resolution.</p>
<p>E-mail</p>	<p>The geographical areas where it would be interesting to replicate the content of the Dashboard are reported in the following figure. However, we also expect changes in the cultivation areas in the future and it might be useful to provide global outlooks on this.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Major <u>Durum Wheat</u> Production Areas</p> <div style="text-align: center;"> </div>
<p>E-mail</p>	<p>It is extremely important to provide information on the skill of the forecast for all the bioclimatic indicators and at the different time scales. In the light of the above, we believe it is useful and important to extend tests, validations to other areas or to the whole national territory, for further refinement of the system.</p> <p>This would also help identify potential common patterns in some areas which could be useful to better tailor the DELPHI tool using the CDS dataset.</p>

4.2 FEEDBACK FROM HORTA ON SEASONAL FORECAST DATA AND CLISAGRI

The structure of the HORTA's Decision Support System (DSS) is made to deal with only one time series of weather data, so the fact that seasonal forecasts are made of an ensemble of several members poses a technical issue for the integration in the system.

Since bias corrected seasonal forecasts have been made available by scientific partners, HORTA began to test its own phenological model with seasonal forecasts issued in several months from November to February, and on several years, for the three selected locations (Ravenna, Jesi and Foggia). Preliminary results show a large variability in the results in different years. There is also variability between the three locations, with Ravenna showing a larger bias in the prediction of the phenological stages than the other two locations. Seasonal forecasts initiated in January or February seem to lead to better simulation of the crop phenology in spring, when the most relevant wheat phenological stages occur, if compared to seasonal forecasts issued in previous months.

A clear definition of the grids considered by the seasonal forecasts (coordinates and centroid) has not yet been provided by the relevant scientific partners of the project. This information can possibly be relevant in understanding the bias in Ravenna, in which the selected location is very close to the sea.

ANNEX A provides the detailed feedback by HORTA agronomy experts on CLISAGRI indicators, which is temporarily substituting the actual user feedback. Users feedback was planned to be collected in a dedicated workshop, which was cancelled due to the pandemic outbreak of Covid-19. Agronomy experts in Horta are involved in the planning and management of field experiments carried out in the experimental and demonstrative farms, with the aim of testing innovations to be transferred to farming practices and to calibrate DSSs' modules. They are also involved in the process of transferring the results to practice by means of the Horta's ICT services, and by the organisation of technical demonstration days focusing on innovation, safety and sustainability in agriculture. In order to collect their feedback, agronomists have been provided with the list of indexes calculated by the CLISAGRI procedure, and were asked to describe the agronomically relevant information provided by each of the indexes, and which decisions can be supported in the durum wheat cropping from a crop manager perspective.

From the technical point of view, the calculation of the CLISAGRI indexes for dynamic periods linked to wheat phenology poses several technical issues. Some of the indexes in CLISAGRI require historical data for their calculation, in order to perform standardisation. For this task, it would be required to run the phenological model on historical weather data for each combination of location and wheat variety, which would require a complex structure of databases and long computational time. This problem is particularly relevant for the potential scalability of the pilot, in case the CLISAGRI bioclimatic indexes need to be calculated on lots of locations and for several wheat varieties.

HORTA requested JRC to evaluate the possibility to implement a method that does not require the calculation of phenological stages on historical data each time the CLISAGRI function is called, in order to reduce the dependence from this kind of data for the index calculation for each combination of location, wheat variety and month in which seasonal forecast are issued.

4.3 FEEDBACK FROM BARILLA ON DELPHI

The national durum wheat production remains an important and extremely relevant asset for pasta production. Barilla heavily relies on the availability and quality of Italian durum wheat.

It remains of utmost importance to have a tool that can return reliable information on yields and therefore on production. The specific orography and diversity of microclimates certainly make the problem complex. Therefore, being able to have a system that guarantees high reliability and that allows the elaboration of forecasts on a seasonal basis, would allow to detect any critical issues.

Looking at the DELPHI calculations and simulations carried out to date, it is clear that there are locations (Foggia) where the system, using "unbiased" data, gives reliable results whilst in other areas this is less true, probably due to what already highlighted above (the high heterogeneity of the Italian territory).

In the light of the above, we believe it is useful and important to extend tests, validations to other areas or to the whole national territory, for further refinement of the system. This would also help identify potential common patterns in some areas which could be useful to better tailor the DELPHI tool using the CDS dataset.

4.4 FEEDBACK ON GRANODURO.NET

The collection of feedback from GRANODURO.NET users, already involved in the co-development process and participating in the previous two workshops reported in D4.1 and 4.6, was planned to take place in May 2020. The scope of the workshop was to collect their feedback on the technical aspects of the tool and its potential usability, as well as to keep the end users informed and involved in the project activities. Due to the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic and consequent restrictions, the workshop could not take place. The organisation of online meetings for feedback collection was not considered feasible due to the unprecedented situation we all had to face and unsuitable to properly meet the scope of the workshop. The meeting with end users is then to be organised in the next months, and it will be planned in such a way to guarantee the safety of the persons involved and to collect useful information for the project activities.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This report summarises the main state of development of the WP4 MED-GOLD tools (CLISAGRI, DELPHI, GRANODURO.NET) for durum wheat with a special emphasis on the implementation of the tools on seasonal forecasts data as well as the new climate information visualization tools (i.e. the Dashboard). This additional tools has been conceived in WP3 as a result of the specific request by the wine sector end-users and has been partially implemented by WP4 as well.

With respect to the previous report CLISAGRI has been substantially developed and extensively described in a scientific article that is currently under review (RD.5). CLISAGRI has been implemented in the seasonal forecast environment developed for MED-GOLD. Some example of this implementation has been reported here. Several agronomists employed by HORTA provided an internal feedback on the list of indicators accounted for by CLISAGRI. Some of the CLISAGRI bioclimatic indicators - the standardized water balance indicators - require the knowledge of the historical climate variability. This class of indicators is very handy as they automatically provide information of the anomalies with respect to the local climate variability in the different stages of the crop growth. However, these indicators are heavy to compute on the seasonal forecast data. Therefore, an approximate solution is identified and it is currently in testing phase.

DELPHI has gone through a deep validation that is partially reported in the previous report and complementarily reported here as well. In addition, DELPHI has been used to estimate the effect of the bias correction procedure to the seasonal forecast data, which is an exclusive result presented and discussed here. A comprehensive result of this activity was provided to BARILLA in order to stimulate the user feedback. The pilot has been proven to meet the expectations, but the reliability of the seasonal forecasts data is a general concern for BARILLA. DELPHI results with bias corrected data, however, have demonstrated a substantial improvement in Southern Italy.

GRANODURO.NET has been subject of an important development phase as well. The implementation of CLISAGRI indicators on historical data, already discussed in the previous report, is briefly reported here as well. Moreover, GRANODURO.NET has integrated the MED-GOLD interface to seasonal forecast data and successfully implemented the phenological model for durum wheat varieties and an indicator for estimating the risk of a number of diseases according to the bias corrected seasonal forecast data. The forecasts of the phenological stages timings are validated using the HORTA observational dataset. The main user feedback on GRANODURO.NET, requiring a dedicated workshop, has been postponed to the next deliverable because of covid19 related restrictions.

BARILLA has evaluated positively the development of the MED-GOLD Dashboard and suggest including more information on the skill of the indicators — a common concern of WP4 partners and end-users — as well as a wider integration with the other MED-GOLD tolls, especially with the CLISAGRI bioclimatic indicators.

Future steps and activities are envisaged for each of the specific MED-GOLD WP4 tools. In general, the extension of the application is expected to cover the global spatial scale and the longer temporal scales (i.e. decadal and multidecadal) in order to estimate the impact of climate variability and change of the areas currently growing durum wheat, in order to identify sustainable adaptation options such as targeted breeding, and in order to identify new suitable areas as well.

In particular, based on the feedback collected from BARILLA a few upgrades on the design of the sectoral tools for durum wheat have been considered and they will be fully reported in DEL4.2. An outline of the components that will be part of the overall design of the sectoral tools can be summarized as follows:

1. Develop an interface between CLISAGRI and the data format compatible with the MED-GOLD Dashboard
2. Assess the feasibility of providing seasonal outlooks at the global or continental scale for the MED-GOLD Dashboard and, at the same time, assess the feasibility of higher resolution seasonal outlooks for the key cultivation areas reported in Table 1.
3. Perform a systematic assessment of the skill of the seasonal outlooks for the durum wheat bio-climatic indicators computed with CLISAGRI, which provide an input both to GRANODURO.NET and to the MED-GOLD dashboard.

BARILLA foresees the application of the MED-GOLD tools at the global scale. This needs to be conducted on the major durum wheat cultivation areas of interest for BARILLA and for new suitable areas that might emerge from the future MED-GOLD analyses and results. This kind of analysis will be conducted mainly with the WOFOST crop model, developed by the JRC, calibrated using the characteristic parameters of the durum wheat varieties (provided by HORTA). The JRC is also planning a suitability estimation based independent from WOFOST through an agroclimatic analysis driven by expert knowledge and artificial intelligence methods.

ANNEX A. ANNEX REPORTING THE TECHNICAL VALUE AND POTENTIAL USABILITY OF THE CLIMATIC INDEXES DEVELOPED FOR THE DURUM WHEAT SECTOR, AS COLLECTED BY HORTA AGRONOMISTS.

Description	Technical value	Potential usability
<p>1. Hydrological balance during pre-sowing period (September and October)</p>	<p>The index can give a support for the decisions on soil tillage at sowing (ploughing vs. no till), on the sowing technique to be applied in the field (conventional vs. direct sowing), and on the application of fertilisers in the pre-sowing period (yes/no). In case drought conditions are foreseen, it is agronomically convenient to opt for no tillage or the application of conservation agriculture techniques, direct sowing and no application of fertilisers before sowing. In case wet conditions are foreseen, it is agronomically convenient to opt for conventional soil tillage and sowing, and to apply fertilisers in the pre-sowing period.</p>	<p>The application of the most suitable technique in the pre-sowing period can have an impact of the yield of the crop, and on the economic balance in the cultivation phase. The possibility to have forecasts for this index can help the farmer in planning the field operations in advance. Forecasts for future years can inform the decisions on the machineries to be purchased, considering that the equipment is different from conservation agriculture to conventional one.</p>
<p>2. Hydrological balance between sowing and emergence</p>	<p>The index can give a support for the decisions on soil tillage at sowing (ploughing vs. no till), on the sowing technique to be applied in the field (conventional vs. direct sowing), and on the application of fertilisers in the pre-sowing period (yes/no). In case drought conditions are foreseen, it is agronomically convenient to opt for no tillage or the application of conservation agriculture techniques, direct sowing and no application of fertilisers before sowing. In case wet conditions are foreseen, it is agronomically convenient to opt for conventional soil tillage and sowing, and to apply fertilisers in the pre-sowing period.</p> <p>In areas affected from the wheat mosaic virus, which is a soil borne disease</p>	<p>The application of the most suitable technique in the pre-sowing period can have an impact of the yield of the crop, and on the economic balance in the cultivation phase. The possibility to have forecasts for this index can help the farmer in planning the field operations in advance. In areas in which the mosaic virus is a problem this index can inform the choice of the wheat variety to be sown, indicating the need to opt for a resistant variety. Forecasts for future years can inform the decisions on the machineries to be purchased, considering that the equipment is different from conservation agriculture to conventional one.</p>

	transmitted by the plasmodiophorid <i>Polymyxa graminis</i> , the index can support wheat variety choice, as wet conditions at wheat emergence favour the infection.	
3. Hydrological balance during tillering	The index can give support for the application of nitrogen fertilisers, which is a critical decision at this stage. In case of cold and rainy winters, the crop will benefit from a higher amount of fertilisers, while it is important not to exceed in nitrogen fertilisation in case winter conditions were mild and dry.	The application of the optimal amount of fertiliser in the tillering phase can have an impact of the yield of the crop. The possibility to have forecasts for this index can help the farmer in planning the field operations in advance, and in the choice of the most suitable fertilisers from (slow release products, or products with inhibitors to minimise fertilisers losses).
4. Hydrological balance between beginning of stem elongation period and end of booting	The index can give support for the application of nitrogen fertilisers, in the period when the crop has the higher demand for nutrients. Information can also be important for the crop protection from diseases, and for the eventual application of irrigation.	The application of the correct amount of fertilisers, the optimal crop protection strategy and the eventual irrigation (in case of need) have direct impact on grain yield and quality. The possibility to have forecasts for this index can help the farmer in planning the field operations in advance, and in the choice of the most suitable fertilisers from (slow release products, or products with inhibitors to minimise fertilisers losses). The possibility to know in advance the foreseen disease pressure can guide the farmer in the choice of particular plant protection products, i.e. on the base of their efficacy.
5. Hydrological balance between beginning of heading period and full maturity	The index can give support for the definition of the crop protection from diseases, in particular for Fusarium Head Blight (FHB). FHB is caused by a complex of fungal species of the genus <i>Fusarium</i> , which infect wheat heads at flowering and can cause both a decrease in grain yield and quality, and the grain contamination from mycotoxins.	The application of the optimal crop protection strategy have direct impact on grain yield and quality. The possibility to have forecasts for this index can help the farmer in planning the field operations in advance, and in the choice of the most suitable crop protection products, i.e. on the base of their efficacy.

<p>6. Hydrological balance between sowing and full maturity</p>	<p>The index can support the decision on: i) soil tillage and sowing technique, ii) fertiliser application, iii) crop protection strategy; iv) need for irrigation, which all together contribute to yield and quality of grains at harvest.</p>	<p>The application of the most suitable tillage and sowing techniques, the correct amount of fertilisers, the optimal crop protection strategy and the eventual irrigation (in case of need) have direct impact on grain yield and quality. The possibility to have forecasts for this index can help the farmer in planning the field operations in advance, and in the choice of the most suitable machinery and equipment, technical inputs such as fertilisers and plant protection products.</p>
<p>7. Rainfall amount during pre-sowing period</p>	<p>The index can give a support for the decisions on soil tillage at sowing (ploughing vs. no till), on the sowing technique to be applied in the field (conventional vs. direct sowing), and on the application of fertilisers in the pre-sowing period (yes/no). In case drought conditions are foreseen, it is agronomically convenient to opt for no tillage or the application of conservation agriculture techniques, direct sowing and no application of fertilisers before sowing. In case wet conditions are foreseen, it is agronomically convenient to opt for conventional soil tillage and sowing, and to apply fertilisers in the pre-sowing period.</p>	<p>The application of the most suitable technique in the pre-sowing period can have an impact of the yield of the crop, and on the economic balance in the cultivation phase. The possibility to have forecasts for this index can help the farmer in planning the field operations in advance. Forecasts for future years can inform the decisions on the machineries to be purchased, considering that the equipment is different from conservation agriculture to conventional one.</p>

<p>8. Number of days with rain above 10 mm during tillering period</p>	<p>The index can give a support for the decisions on nitrogen fertiliser application, as these amount of rain is need for the fertiliser activation in the days after its application in field. The index is also relevant for the application of chemical for weed management, which also require rains to be activated in the soil. The index can also give information on the possibility to apply the technique of legumes intercropping in wheat. This technique consists in the sowing of legumes in the wheat inter-row at wheat tillering, and benefits from harrowing after the distribution of legumes' seeds.</p>	<p>The application of the optimal amount of fertiliser in the tillering phase can have an impact of the yield of the crop. The index can help the identification of the best time to perform fertilisation, application of chemical for weeding, and the sowing of intercrops in the wheat field. The possibility to have forecasts for this index can help the farmer in planning the field operations in advance, in the most suitable conditions and with the most suitable products.</p>
<p>9. Number of days with rain above 40 mm during tillering</p>	<p>The index can give support for the application of nitrogen fertilisers, which is a critical decision at this stage. In case of cold and rainy winters, the crop will benefit from an higher amount of fertilisers, while it is important not to exceed in nitrogen fertilisation in case winter conditions were mild and dry.</p>	<p>The application of the optimal amount of fertiliser in the tillering phase can have an impact of the yield of the crop. The possibility to have forecasts for this index can help the farmer in planning the field operations in advance, and in the choice of the most suitable fertilisers from (slow release products, or products with inhibitors to minimise fertilisers losses).</p>
<p>10. Number of days with rain above 5 mm between beginning of heading and full maturity</p>	<p>The index can give support for the definition of the crop protection from diseases, in particular for Fusarium Head Blight (FHB). FHB is caused by a complex of fungal species of the genus <i>Fusarium</i>, which infect wheat heads at flowering and can cause both a decrease in grain yield and quality, and the grain contamination from mycotoxins.</p>	<p>The application of the optimal crop protection strategy have direct impact on grain yield and quality. The possibility to have forecasts for this index can help the farmer in planning the field operations in advance, and in the choice of the most suitable crop protection products, i.e. on the base of their efficacy.</p>

<p>11. Number of days with rain above 40 mm between beginning of heading and full maturity</p>	<p>The index can give indication on the expected yield and quality of grain at harvest. In case of low rain amount in this period, quality of harvested grain will probably be high (protein content, hectoliter weight, yield), while in case of high rain amount quality will probably be low (fungal infections, i.e. black point problems and/or mycotoxin contamination, and low hectoliter weight).</p>	<p>The possibility to have forecasts for this index can help elevators to plan in advance the most suitable storage strategy for grain lots with different qualitative characteristics.</p>
<p>12 Maximum number of consecutive days with rain above 5 mm between beginning of heading and end of flowering</p>	<p>The index can give support for the definition of the crop protection from diseases, in particular for Fusarium Head Blight (FHB). FHB is caused by a complex of fungal species of the genus <i>Fusarium</i>, which infect wheat heads at flowering and can cause both a decrease in grain yield and quality, and the grain contamination from mycotoxins.</p>	<p>The application of the optimal crop protection strategy have direct impact on grain yield and quality. The possibility to have forecasts for this index can help the farmer in planning the field operations in advance, and in the choice of the most suitable crop protection products, i.e. on the base of their efficacy.</p>
<p>13. Maximum number of consecutive days with rain above 5 mm between end of flowering and full maturity</p>	<p>The index can give indication on the expected yield and quality of grain at harvest. In case of low rain amount in this period, quality of harvested grain will probably be high (protein content, hectoliter weight, yield), while in case of high rain amount quality will probably be low (fungal infections, i.e. black point problems and/or mycotoxin contamination, and low hectoliter weight).</p>	<p>The possibility to have forecasts for this index can help elevators to plan in advance the most suitable storage strategy for grain lots with different qualitative characteristics.</p>
<p>14. Number of days with minimum daily temperature below 2 deg. C between booting and flowering</p>	<p>The index can give an indication on the possibility to have frost risk and related damage to the plants, leading to a reduction of grain yield.</p>	<p>The possibility to have forecasts for this index can give the farmer an indication on the expected yield.</p>

15. Number of hot days with maximum daily temperature above 28 deg. C between end of stem elongation and end of flowering	The index can give support the decision on the application of irrigation, which can help counterbalancing the effect of the heat stress, with positive effect on yield.	The possibility to have forecasts for this index give the farmer the possibility to plan the application of irrigation, and indication on the expected yield and quality.
16. Number of hot days with maximum daily temperature above 28 deg. C between during grain filling period	The index can give an indication on the possibility to have heat stress for the plants, impacting on grain yield and quality.	The possibility to have forecasts for this index can give the farmer an indication on the expected yield and on the quality.

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